

Ethovision: Forced Swim Task

Setting up Video Analysis

- Click “New,” “Name,” then “Ok”
- Go to “Experiment Settings”
 - Number of subjects: 1
 - Select “Activity Analysis”
- Go to “Arena Settings 1” → “Arena Settings 1” → then click “Browse” and open the video
- Once you open the video, click “Grab”
- If 1. If “Draw Scale to Calibrate” is selected: draw line across top of beaker → type 13 (cm) → OK
- Select 2. Select “Shape and Draw Arena” → select Create Closed Polyline button on top bar
 - Click in each corner to outline beaker excluding top lip and double click last corner to outline arena
- Click 4. Validate setup → OK
- Rename “Arena Settings 1” to the number of the mouse in the video
- Go to “Trial Control Settings 1” → “Trial Control Settings 1”
 - Click box next to “Time” condition; change label to “Start” → OK
 - Go to “Settings” for “Start” and under condition is met: After: _____ (enter # of seconds in video until the mouse is in the arena and no person is in the field of view) → OK
 - Delete existing arrow connecting Rule Begin → Action (right click arrow, click delete)
 - Click from gray middle of Rule Begin to Condition (Start) to connect boxes with arrow. Repeat for Condition → Action.
 - Click Settings for “Time (2)” and rename condition to “Stop”
 - Under condition is met: After: _____ (enter 6 minutes) → OK
- Rename “Trial Control Settings 1” to the number of the mouse in the video
- Go to “Detection Settings 1” → “Detection Settings 1”
 - Scroll to part of video with mouse in view
 - Click “Activity” on right menu
 - Compression artifacts filter: ON
 - Background noise filter: (to get rid of scoring moving water) (Play video)
 - Keep increasing until no water movement scored and mainly paws are detected
 - Activity threshold: slide bar to optimize when actual movement occurs
 - Detection → Advanced
 - Range: move left button to 255 (255-255) → computer will only focus on activity and not tracking the mouse
 - Rename Detection Settings 1 to “Detect” (because all will use the same one)
 - Click Save to save the file

Repeat for all other animals:

- Click on previous Animal ID under Arena Settings (1): right click → duplicate → name as next Animal ID
- Click Grab Background Image Button in bottom right → Find video → Grab → move Arena and scale bar as needed → do NOT resize or redraw them
- Click 4. Validate Setup
- Under Trial Control Settings (1) duplicate and name with next Animal ID and adjust the time delay under Start settings for that animal's video.
 - Apply the new settings only in the current Trial Control Settings
- No need to duplicate or alter Detection Settings (1) → click Save to save the file

Generating Data from Video Analysis

Once all animals for that study are complete

- Go to “Trial List”
 - Add variable animal ID
 - Add trials and fill in table: select video, Arena Settings, Trial Control Settings for each animal (all animals will have the only “Detect” for Detection Settings)
- Go to “Acquisition”
 - Turn on Smoothing (Track Smoothing Profiles)
 - Track all planned trials
 - Ready for Start (Red circle button) → videos are analyzed
- Analysis → Data Profiles
 - Result 1 → settings → check results per time bin (2 min) → check ignore last time bin if incomplete → OK
- Click “Analysis Profile 1”
 - Body → Activity State → Number of States: 3
 - Change: High: 1.00%; Inactive: 0.10%
 - Trial Statistics: Latency to First + Cumulative Duration + Cumulative Duration (%) → Add
 - Body → Activity → Add
- Integrated Visualization
 - Play video to see if settings for highly active vs. inactive are accurate → unclick Feature Trial to get rid of red line
 - Note Activity % during video when animal is mobile vs. immobile and use as guide to adjust in Analysis Profile → Activity State
 - You may need to clear trial and readjust Detection Setting: Activity Threshold + Background Noise
 - Reenter Trial List → Acquire Videos
 - Switch between watching video under Integrated Visualization and Analysis Profile → Activity State Thresholds until levels of activity are being accurately detected
- Results → Statistics and Charts → Calculate → Export Data

Sample Settings:

- Detection Settings → Activity: Threshold: 8; Background Noise: 5; Compression: ON
- Analysis Profile → Activity State Thresholds: High >1%, immobile <0.1%